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Gentamicin sulphate-*Nigella sativa* oil-loaded poly(trimethylene carbonate-co-caprolactone) beads: a promising treatment for osteomyelitis

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Background: Biofilm formation on the prosthetic implant in osteomyelitis poses a great challenge to clinicians. A biodegradable, antibiofilm polymer bead is of great interest to osteomyelitis treatment since current treatments only accentuate the biofilm formation. The antimicrobial properties of gentamicin sulphate have been verified against different types of bacteria including *Staphylococcus aureus*; interest in gentamicin has been renewed to impregnate it into the biodegradable polymer for osteomyelitis.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antibacterial properties of poly(trimethylene carbonate-co-caprolactone) (PTMCC) beads loaded with the fusion of gentamicin sulphate-*Nigella sativa* oil as an emulsion (GNE). **Material and methods:** PTMCC, a biodegradable and biocompatible polymer was first used to fabricate the beads. Impregnation of the GNE into the PTMCC beads was performed using a double-emulsion solvent evaporation method. The fabricated beads were tested on the Mueller Hinton agar plate containing *S. aureus* ATCC 29213. At each 24 hours interval, beads were transferred to new agar plate to observe the sustained release of GNE. **Results:** We observed average zone of inhibition 17.36 ± 0.82 mm for gentamicin-containing beads, 6.50 ± 0.39 mm for *Nigella sativa* oil (NSO) containing beads and no inhibition for PTMCC alone beads. The release of gentamicin from beads was sustained, and release amount of gentamicin was almost similar every day as reflected by the zone of inhibition. NSO-containing beads showed inhibition on the first day only. **Conclusion:** The

GNE-loaded PTMCC beads showed significant zone of inhibition over 15 days, indicating potency to be used in implant surgery of osteomyelitis.

Keywords: PTMCC; *Nigella sativa*; gentamicin sulphate; osteomyelitis; biofilm.

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Development and evaluation of novel gastroretentive drug delivery system based on combination of natural polymer and rice bran wax

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Background: Although variety of polymeric substances and waxes are available to serve as components of Gastroretentive Drug Delivery System (GRDDS), there is a continuous need to develop new, safe and effective components. In the present study, an attempt was made to use the combination of natural polymer and rice bran wax in the formulation of GRDDS as this combination has not been reported in the literature. **Objective:** Gastroretentive tablets were formulated with an intention to control drug delivery and to enhance the gastric residence time of drug in GIT. **Material and methods:** Famotidine was selected as a model drug for formulation of gastroretentive tablets and the procured rice bran wax was characterized for various physiochemical parameters. Tablets were prepared by using hot melt granulation technique resulting in six different formulations and the prepared formulations were evaluated for pre-compression and post-compression parameters. Factorial design (3²) was employed to optimize formulation. Nine formulations were prepared using two independent variables as amount of Guar Gum (X₁) and RBW (X₂). The floating lag time (FLT), Swelling Index (SI) and Percentage Cumulative Drug Release (% CDR) were selected as dependent variables. **Results:** The results of the preliminary trial batches indicated that the gastroretentive tablets containing natural polymer and rice bran wax

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